

Table 1. Genera of nematodes found in deepwater rice fields near the capitals of Prajinburi (PJB) and Ayuthaya (AYT) provinces, Thailand.

Genus	In the soil before planting		Before floodwaters				After floodwater recedes				In the soil at harvest	
	PJB	AYT	soil		Root		soil		Root		PJB ^a	AYT
			PJB	AYT	PJB	AYT	PJB	AYT	PJB	AYT		
<i>Hirschmanniella</i>	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X		X
<i>Tylenchorhynchus</i>	X	X	X	X			X	X				X
<i>Meloidogyne</i>		X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X		X
<i>Helicotylenchus</i>	X	X	X	X								
<i>Tylenchus</i>	X	X	X	X								
<i>Aphelenchoides</i>		X										X
<i>Criconemoides</i>	X				X			X				X
<i>Aphelenchus</i>		X										
<i>Ditylenchus</i>		X			X			X				
<i>Pratylenchus</i>								X		X		
<i>Lengidorus</i>								X				

^aNo sampling.

Table 2. Average percentage of three genera of nematodes obtained from soil samples collected from deepwater rice fields during 1979 in Prajinburi (PJB) and Ayuthaya (AYT) provinces, Thailand.

Genus	Nematodes (av %)												Percent of total population in soil
	In the soil before planting		Before floodwater				After floodwater recedes				In the soil at harvest		
	PJB	AYT	Soil		Roots		Soil		Roots		PJB ^a	AYT	
			PJB	AYT	PJB	AYT	PJB	AYT	PJB	AYT			
<i>Hirschmanniella</i>	22.5	13.1	9.1	1.2	'few'	0	18.6	7.0	'many'	'many'	22.4		11.4
<i>Tylenchorhynchus</i>	8.1	5.7	22.1	17.7	0	0	11.8	16.1	-	-	18.5		41.5
<i>Meloidogyne</i>	-	0.4	19.9	1.0	0	0	4.0	13.6	'many'	'few'	61.0		47.1

^aNo sampling.

roots after the flood in both provinces. *Ditylenchus*, a predominant rice parasitic nematode in some countries, was found

only in Ayuthaya in small amounts. Only *Aphelenchoides* was found in the leaves, and in small numbers. Plans are

to continue this work and conduct surveys in additional provinces during the 1980 growing season. ■

Pest management and control INSECTS

Egg parasites of yellow stem borer in southern Sri Lanka

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A survey of parasites of yellow stem borer *Tryporyza incertulas* Wlk. eggs was conducted in 1979 in southern Sri Lanka. Parasites were reared from egg masses in June-July and November-December, during the major cultivation seasons. Parasitization of yellow borer egg masses averaged 88%. The parasites were identified from IBP Handbook 14 as *Trichogramma minutum* Riley,

Parasitization of yellow stem borer egg masses in southern Sri Lanka, 1979.

Location	Egg masses	
	Total sampled (no.)	Parasitization (%)
Kamburupitiya	37	86
Matara	26	81
Ambalantota	26	81
Kekanadura	69	97
Denipitiya	13	77

Tetrastichus schoenobii Ferr, *Tetrastichus israeli* M. & K, *Telenomus dignus* Gahan. *T. dignus* was the most prevalent species, occurring on more than 65% of the total egg masses counted (see table). ■

Survival of rice bug *Leptocorisa oratorius* on graminaceous weeds during the fallow period between rice cropping in Sri Lanka

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The rice bug *Leptocorisa oratorius* in both the nymphal and adult stage prevents rice grain formation by sucking the milky juice of developing grains. The ability of the pest to survive on an alternate host poses a major problem in control strategies. A survey was carried out to find the alternate hosts of the rice

bug in southern Sri Lanka. The pest was detected feeding on graminaceous weeds, and laboratory trials on the insect's survival on the following weeds gave positive results: *Panicum repens*, *Panicum maximum*, *Echinochloa crus-galli*, *Echinochloa colona*, *Dactyloctenium aegyptium*, *Alloteropsis cimicina*, *Axonopus affinis*, *Chloris*

barbata, *Paspalidium punctatum*, *Brachiaria miliiformis*, *Brachiaria mutica*, *Ischaemum muticum*, *Setaria glauca*, *Bothriochloa pertusa*, *Eleusine indica*, *Dicanthelium clandestinum*.

The weed population on bunds and in the rice paddies could facilitate insect survival and help continue its life cycle, especially during the off-season. The

insect survived during the off-season of rice cropping (Jul-Sep) soon after the yala season (Apr-Jul) and before the maha season (Nov-Feb) which are the main rice cropping seasons in Sri Lanka, Since weeds grow in rice fields throughout the year, eliminating them on bunds and rice fields will help in effective insect pest management. ■

***Euscyrtus concinnus* (Orthoptera: Gryllidae) – a new rice pest in the Philippines**

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A survey of irrigated rice fields in Batangas province revealed the occurrence of a leaf- and stem-feeding gryllid recently identified as *Euscyrtus concinnus* de Haan (Orthoptera: Gryllidae). This is the first account of the insect as a rice pest in the Philippines.

E. concinnus makes irregular to longitudinal holes in the leaves, leaving the margins almost intact. Intense stem feeding sometimes causes deadhearts (photo 1). An average of 18-34 nymphs and adults/m² were found during November. Although both are pestiferous, the nymphs cause more

2. Adults of *E. concinnus*. female (left) and male (right).

damage than adults and prefer to feed on seedbeds and transplanted rice. The pest does not generally attack the rice plant beyond 75 days after transplanting, but in the absence of alternate hosts or young rice plants, it may feed on the very young rice panicles.

The following grasses and sedges were observed to be alternate hosts: *Echinochloa* spp., *Dactyloctenium aegyptium* (L.) Beauv., *Cyperus rotundus* L., *Digitaria sanguinalis* (L.) Scop., *Eleusine indica* (L.) Gaertn., *Paspalidium flavidum* (Retz.) A. Camus, and *Rottboellia exaltata* L.f.

The adults (photo 2) are 1-1.8 cm in length and pale brown in color, with long antennae and legs that easily detach from the body. The females are longer than the males and can easily be distinguished by their long, spear-shaped ovipositor. This species is also recorded in India, Thailand, and Bangladesh as a pest of rice. ■

1. Damage on the stem (resulting in deadheart) and leaves caused by feeding of *E. concinnus* nymphs and adults.

Stylectomy of plant-sucking insects using a YAG laser to collect rice phloem sap

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The lack of technique to selectively collect phloem sap from the rice plant has hampered investigation of the chemical basis of plant resistance to planthoppers and leafhoppers.

The use of YAG (Yttrium Aluminum Garnet) laser made it possible to sever the stylet bundle (stylectomy) of the brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* and green leafhopper *Nephotettix cincticeps* while in the process of probing the rice plant. This allowed pure rice phloem sap to be collected from the excised stylets for the first time.

The laser beam (energy 0.1 joule and pulse width 0.2 m sec) emitted from the YAG laser system (Toshiba Inc., model LAY-508, wavelength 1.064 μm) was focused by a condensing lens and hit the proboscis of the insect feeding on the rice leaf sheath (Fig. 1). An aperture reduced the diameter of the beam so that the beam spot on the proboscis at the focal point in front of the lens was about 0.13 mm in diameter (Fig. 1,2).

An optical apparatus was attached to the system to display the image of the probing insect on the plant onto a cathode ray tube. By observing this image, the focused beam was aimed to hit the upper portion of the proboscis where the stylets are located (Fig. 2). The beam is also aimed to hit the halfway point of the proboscis between the plant tissue and the head of the insect.

Almost every pulsing successfully